

Figure 1

a

b

c

d

e

f

Figure 1: Overview of data sets and neighborhood representation. (a) Phenotype composition of biological samples, where samples S1 through S5 and S6 through S9 are responders and non-responders of the cross-validation dataset respectively, and samples ST1 and ST2, and ST3 and ST4 are responders and non-responders of the testing set respectively. (b-e) Construction of NH datapoints. Single cell protein data obtained through cyclic immunofluorescence imaging (b) were segmented and phenotyped to obtain (single) cell positions and phenotypes (c). For each cancer cell, all cells within a radius of 200 μ m were included in that cell's NH. For each identified phenotype, a radial distribution was calculated based on these collections of cells (d). For model training and inference, these collections of phenotype radial density distributions were split into a row normalized distribution matrix with a row sum of one, and a magnitude vector containing the previous row sum (e). (f) Sample composition of the cross-validation and test data sets. The values shown represent the number of neighborhood (NH) datapoints contributed by each sample.

Figure 2

Figure 2: Model architectures and validation strategy. For training of the multiple instance learning (MIL) model, neighborhood (NH) data points were collected in bags (a). The size of each bag was evaluated using cross-validation. Each bag was constructed from data points of one sample and inherited the sample’s response label. The three model architectures explored in this study are shown in (b). For each model architecture, an autoencoder was used to project the neighborhood data points to a latent representation followed by differing MIL modules. For the mean-vote and attention-vote models, predictive scores were calculated for individual NH data points followed by aggregation using mean and attention weighted mean respectively. In the bag-embedding model, the individual NH feature vectors in latent space were combined to a single bag-embedding from which the bag score was determined. For model validation, a sample-level logistic ranking loss was calculated (c). The model first calculated the bag predictions of the validation/testing set. For each sample, the average of these predictions was calculated

and transformed to logit space. For each responder / non-responder, a logistic ranking loss was calculated, resulting of a score of $\ln(2)$ if both responders and non-responders received an equal score, below $\ln(2)$ if the samples were separated and ranked correctly, and above $\ln(2)$ if the samples were separated but ranked incorrectly.

Figure 3

Figure 3: Cross-validation model selection and robustness. (a) Three different model architectures were evaluated across every combination of hyperparameters: bag size (100, 200), the number of neighborhood bins (10, 20), the size of the latent space (10, 20), and training dropout rate (0.1, 0.3). Each dot represents the mean score across all folds for a single hyperparameter combination. The red dotted line represents a logistic ranking loss of $\ln(2)$ indicating no separation between responders and non-responders. (b) Hyperparameter analysis for the bag-embedding model architecture with the eight top performing models. The hyper parameters: bag size (100, 200), number of neighborhood bins (10, 20), size of the latent space (10, 20), and L2 kernel weight loss ($1e-5$, $1e-4$) were tested across all combinations with the red line representing a logistic ranking loss of $\ln(2)$. (c) Benchmarking of top performing hyperparameters investigating three different kernel numbers across three different seeds. Each dot represents a single fold, with color

representing the model-initialization and data set generation seed. (d) Stability across 12 different seeds for the two best performing hyperparameters. Each dot represents the mean logistic ranking loss of all folds in one seed. The dashed line represents a logistic ranking loss of $\ln(2)$. (e) Fold-difficulty heatmap for the top performing hyperparameter. The color and top number represent the mean logistic ranking loss across 12 different seeds, with the standard deviation given below in parentheses.

Figure 4

Figure 4: Evaluation of the trained ensemble on a held-out test set. An ensemble of 12 models was trained using 12 different seeds and the top performing hyperparameters of cross validation. The sample-level predicted scores on the held-out test set is shown in (a), with black and red dots representing the predicted scores of sub-models and the ensemble respectively. A prediction threshold of 0.5 is shown as a dotted line. The sample level model performance metrics: pair AUC, pair logistic ranking loss (Pair LRL), and binary cross entropy are shown in (b), with black and red dots representing sub-model and ensemble performances respectively. The ensemble was applied on individual neighborhood data points with the predicted score distributions shown in (c). The violin

plot illustrates the observation density across the responder-like score range, with the mean and median over all cancer cell neighborhoods in one sample represented as a red dot and dash respectively. A threshold for high-scoring neighborhoods was set at a responder-line score of 0.75. In (d), for each sample, the fraction of neighborhoods receiving a score above this threshold is shown.

Figure 5

Figure 5: Biological composition of high- and low-scoring neighborhoods. The trained

ensemble was used to assign responder-like scores to single cancer cell neighborhoods (NHs). NHs with a score of over 0.75 and under 0.25 were classified as high- or low-scoring NHs respectively. The average number of cells for each immune phenotype found in the high- and low-scoring NHs of a sample are shown in (a). (b) shows the fraction of NHs in a sample that contain at least one cell of each phenotype. For all NHs that contain at least one cell of each phenotype within their radius, the average minimum distance to the central cancer cell is shown in (c).

Figure 6

Figure 6: Spatial responder-like score heatmaps. The trained ensemble was used to assign responder-like scores to single cancer cell neighborhoods. For each sample, cancer cells with valid neighborhoods were plotted by their spatial location and colored by the mean score they received by the ensemble. Remaining cells of a different phenotype and cancer cells with incomplete neighborhoods were plotted in gray. In (a), the heatmaps for responder samples S2 and ST1, as well as non-responder samples S8 and ST4 are shown. The red scale-bars show a distance of 500 μm . A high-scoring NH from sample S2 and a low-scoring NH from sample S8 are shown in (b) and (c) respectively. The spatial locations of these NHs within the samples are marked in (a).

Table 1: Markers used for hierarchical phenotyping

Cell type	Cell markers
Cancer cells	CK+
Stromal cells	CK- aSMA+
Endothelial cells	CK- CD45- CD31+
Macrophages	CK- aSMA- CD45+ CD8- CD4- (CD68+ OR CD163+)
Dendritic cells	CK- aSMA- CD45+ CD8- CD4- CD68- CD163- HLA-DR+
CD8+ T cells	CK- aSMA- CD45+ CD8+
CD4+ T cells	CK- aSMA- CD45+ CD8- CD4+
Regulatory T cells	CK- aSMA- CD45+ CD8- CD4+ FoxP3+
Other immune cells	CK- aSMA- CD45+ CD8- CD4- CD68- CD163- HLA-DR

Table 2: Cross validation hyperparameters

CV round	Hyperparameters varied	Fixed hyperparameters
1	Architecture: mean-vote, vote-attention, bag-embedding NH bins: 10/20 Bag size: 100/200 Latent size: 10/20 Dropout: 0.1/0.3	L2 weight: 1e-4 Learning rate: 1e-4 Reconstruction weight: 1 Prediction weight: 1 N kernels: 8 Seed=0
2	NH bins: 10/20 Bag size: 100/200 Latent size: 10/20 L2 weight: 1e-5/1e-4	Architecture: bag-embedding Dropout: 0.3 Learning rate: 1e-4 N kernels:8 Reconstruction weight: 1 Prediction weight: 1 Seed: 0
3	N kernels: 4/8/16 Seed: 1–3	Architecture: bag-embedding Dropout: 0.3 Learning rate:1e-4 N kernels:8 NH bins: 10 Bag size: 100 Reconstruction weight: 1 Prediction weight: 1 L2 weight: 1e-4
4	N kernels: 4/8 Seed: 1–12	Architecture: bag-embedding Dropout: 0.3 Learning rate:1e-4 N kernels:8 NH bins: 10 Bag size: 100 Reconstruction weight: 1 Prediction weight: 1 L2 weight: 1e-4

Table 3: Hyperparameters of final ensemble

Hyperparameter	Value
Architecture	Bag-embedding
Dropout	0.3
Learning rate	1e-4
NH bins	10
Bag size	100
Reconstruction weight	1
Prediction weight	1
L2 weight	1e-4
N kernels	4
Seed	1-12

Supplementary Table 1: Overview over cyclic immunofluorescence rounds

Round	488nm channel	555nm channel	647nm channel	750nm channel
1	ColVI	CD31	CD4	ECad
2	Desmin	B7H4	CD8	CD20
3	aSMA	CD68	PD1	CD45
4	Vim	AXL	PD-L1	FoxP3
5	R6c2	Ca9	CD163	Ki67
6	CKs	Bcl2	CD44	HLADR
7	-	PDGFR	MMP9	GATA3
8	-	CD11c	Sting	CD11b